

La Trobe Law Tech Submission

on the

Online Safety Legislative Reform Discussion Paper

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Re: Online Safety Legislative Reform Discussion Paper (2019)

La Trobe LawTech appreciates to opportunity to provide responses to the consultation into Online Safety Legislative Reform.

La Trobe LawTech (<https://www.latrobe.edu.au/cybersecurity/expertise/lawtech>), based at the La Trobe Law School, was formed in 2017 by a multidisciplinary group of scholars working nationally and internationally on different aspects of data technologies, law and society.

Our expertise relevant to this consultation includes areas such as: compliance through design and compliance by design, innovation and regulation's impact on legal rights, hate speech, artificial intelligence, national security, public policy, access to justice and privacy.

From that basis we welcome the consolidation of the relevant legislation as well as the new powers proposed for the eSafety Commissioner, especially those would allow eSafety to act on content hosted overseas and on intermediary services.

We do not believe consistent application of online safety schemes across substantively different types of service would be a good approach as it would force a lower standard to apply (for the sake of consistency with others) to services of a type, scale and risk to warrant a higher bar. We draw the analogy to the exclusion of small business operators in the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth),¹ as well as the

¹ 6C(1)

exceptions to this exclusion which apply in certain prescribed circumstances based on higher risk or a range of public policy considerations.²

We would welcome greater transparency by platforms, however, there is a fundamental weakness is companies providing their own transparency data. There is a need for an obligation that such data be truthful, accurate, and auditable or at least verifiable through third party sampling / verification techniques. More may need to be done to enable work that seeks to verify such data or to highlight gaps and blind spots.

We welcome the expansion of the cyber abuse scheme to adults, but have concerns with the proposed application. We note a range of questions in relation to response times for different kinds of harms. In general, any clock on a response time should start from the time the user notifies the platform, not from when eSafety notifies them. Unless there is a penalty for failing to respond to user complaints there is the risk of incentivising the focus only on complaints that come via government, turning eSafety and its capacity into a bottleneck that allows platforms to avoid having to respond in a timely fashion to most harmful content.

The functions of the eSafety Commissioner until now have included: (i) the cyberbullying scheme that addresses cyberbullying of an Australian child; (ii) the image-based abuse scheme that addresses the non-consensual sharing of intimate images; and (iii) the online content scheme for regulating access to illegal and harmful online content ('prohibited content' and 'potential prohibited content').

Even agreeing with the overall regulation plan, the three schemes that applied so far raise potential concerns related to free speech, the protection of citizens' civil rights, and their effectiveness and efficacy when applied in a non-nuanced manner or where expectations are raised and not met. The proposals seek to address some of these concerns but a more holistic and ongoing approach is needed and greater input from the public, civil society organisations and experts must be part of this process.

Safety by Design (SbD) could be understood as Safety *through* Design (StD), i.e. effective collaboration among service providers, regulators and social stakeholders (including security companies and civil society organisations ranging from specialists focused on digital and online rights and responsibilities, to general human rights organisations) to provide better technological services that support and align with regulatory measures over the whole lifecycle of the services. SbD and the Online Safety Charter

² E.g. Privacy Act 1988 (Cth) S 6D(4) and 6E

are indeed complementary, but this link could be improved with the participation of the AI & Law community. Some expert platforms could help as well with (i) the automatic detection of online misinformation; (ii) the investigation of misinformation propagation patterns and their prediction, (iii) validation and fact-checking, (iv) the identification of the most effective intervention strategies, and (v) the provision of empowering tools to prevent not only misinformation but *misperception* of citizens, consumers, and end-users.³ These issues would sit broadly within an online safety remit. If the eSafety Commissioner were to become a standalone agency, it would need to deal with all aspects of eSafety and cannot be expected to do so effectively without appropriate collaboration with civil society and academia.

It is worth mentioning that online hate speech can occur in many ways through a variety of individual and collective behaviours. It is broader than just cyberbullying. This is a difficult problem with no easy solutions. Granularity should be addressed. Online hate speech is a key focus in overseas regulation. Online disinformation (including political misinformation), fake news, rumours (gossiping), and what Cass Sunstein popularised some time ago as "availability cascades" (e.g. the cases of Love Canal, the Alar scare, TWA Flight 800...) are drawing the increasing interest of AI researchers.

We do not believe that legal measures (content removal, prohibitions, sanctions or even contracts) are sufficient to achieve the measure of e-safety that society requires. Legal measures should be combined with the implementation of technical regulatory toolkits, e.g. social machines coordinating human and autonomous agents' intelligence, able to escalate, and aimed at the monitoring, control and especially *prevention* of bad informational practices. Fact-checking analytical processes on the information flows should be incorporated. The general objectives of (i) preventing online harms; (ii) promoting online safety; and (iii) protecting Australians online, will benefit from a closer cooperation with the AI & Law community. In addition, legal measures need to be crafted with care to not to impede actions that facilitate the underlying purpose of the Act and its objectives.

Kind regards,

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Prepared in a personal capacity by the above members of the La Trobe Law Tech Group.

³ Cf. Fernandez, Miriam, and Harith Alani. "Online misinformation: Challenges and future directions." In *Companion Proceedings of the The Web Conference 2018*, pp. 595-602. 2018.

Question 1 to 2

The high-level objectives should be expanded to clearly express Australia's commitment to support international and multilateral online safety efforts.

The principles speak about government and industry. Civil society also plays a vital role in this space. See for example the work of the Online Hate Prevention Institute. The statement of regulatory policy should acknowledge the role of civil society and the knowledge produced by research teams, research institutes and universities, and make a clear commitment to working in partnership and collaboration with civil society, as well as to achieving the broad objectives through support of civil society.

Questions 3 to 6

The concept of Basic Online Safety Expectations is useful for large platforms. Applying it universally to social media may be problematic. It can, for example, stifle innovation and competition by squeezing newer and small companies out of the market place, or making the barriers to entry too onerous. There is also a potential definitional problem over what qualifies as a social media platform.

It would be more effective to have higher basic expectations and only apply them to platforms which have a larger impact. The required level of impact should be much lower than in the correct scheme, but it should be limited to those platforms with significant userbase in Australia and which are large enough that placing expectations on them would be reasonable. This is the equivalent of the threshold in relation to GST registration, or the small business exemption under the Privacy Act. Below the threshold it should be sufficient for the eSafety Commissioner to be able to request details of a company's policies (if any) and answers to questions posed to the company. This information can be used to provide advice and recommendations to the Australian public.

Consideration should be given to clarifying the concept of a "social media platform" to prevent definitional uncertainties if this approach continues.

Questions 7 to 10

The expansion of the scheme is reasonable provided the burden does not prevent new market entrants or stifle innovation. A tiered scheme in which commitments can be met by the smallest

services by simply providing a public point of contact for users would introduce a measure of regulatory flexibility.

The takedown period may be longer for platforms that are not currently part of the scheme. Expanding the reach while also reducing the expected response time may impose overly onerous compliance burdens. It would be appropriate to introduce different time periods for different types of platforms and for different types of communications within different platforms. The removal of public cyberbullying content may, for example, require a faster response than the communication of cyberbullying content in private to the victim.

Comparing the Australian scheme and international schemes highlights a reporting and action discrepancy. Some schemes require a response within 24 hours from the time a user reports it to the platform, while in others (like this scheme) action is required within 24 hours after a report is filed by government. Ideally action should be triggered by users and by governments and the time period should start running whenever the first report on the matter is filed. Channelling reports only via government is problematic. It is expensive, requiring appropriate resources to respond in a timely manner. In practice, it will give rise to a bottle-neck and prevent appropriate, timely action.

Question 11 to 15

In terms of time limits we reiterate our comments above. The expected removal times should be from when a user reports the content to the platform or service. The expected response time may vary by the type of service / platform, depending primarily on the impact it is likely to cause.

We have reservations about the proposed implementation of a cyberbullying scheme for adults. The fact eSafety cannot order a takedown of content that is likely to breach s 474.17 of the Commonwealth Criminal Code is the problem which we believe should be addressed here. Closing this gap would meet the underlying goal of providing online safety for all Australians. We do not believe a victim's "vulnerability" or "resilience", or indeed the specific impact on the targeted individual, are relevant elements.

Section 474.17 of the Commonwealth Criminal Code outlines an offence that occurs when a service is used and "the person does so in a way (whether by the method of use or the content of a communication, or both) that reasonable persons would regard as being, in all the circumstances, menacing, harassing or offensive". The test is objective, not based on the perpetrator's subjective intention, nor on subjective impact felt by the victim. The same test should apply to a take down order, with some minimal changes.

We would recommend empowering the eSafety Commission to issue a takedown notice in relation to content which “(a) reasonable persons would regard as being, in all the circumstances, menacing, harassing, or offensive, and (b) where the continued availability of the content online is likely, in all the circumstances, to have a profound and serious effect”. The addition of element (b) draws on judicial interpretation of S18C of the *Racial Discrimination Act 1975* (Cth),⁴ which has provided the necessarily protection to balance protection against harm and freedom of expression.⁵

The additional requirement of a “profound and serious effect” provides a reasonable balance to protect free speech. We note that under such an approach, the profound and serious effect need not be an effect on the intended victim but could, for example, include a likely loss of public confidence in the effectiveness of the eSafety Commissioner or the spread of fear among other members of the community, even if the victim explicitly states they are unaffected. As a takedown order is far less serious a consequence than a prison term, it is appropriate to decide the matter on the balance of probabilities. This was the approach suggested by French J in *Bropho v Human Rights & Equal Opportunity Commission*.⁶

The reference to a “particular adult” is also problematic and not part of s 474.17. It is a part of the children’s scheme which is no needed when converting the scheme to more general application to protect all Australians. Online violence against women, as highlighted in the consultation paper, may target women in general or women in a particular industry as well as individual women (as occurred in Gamegate). Hate speech against other groups which face elevated levels of cyber bullying and online hate could similarly have a profound and serious effect. Cyber racism, religious vilification, homophobia, transphobia and attacks on people with disabilities are just some of the ways in which people and society are harmed online though both cyberbullying of them personally and hate speech attacking the group generally. There is no reason to prevent the eSafety Commissioner having a power to takedown this content as well, particularly when both the transparency reporting and the schemes in other countries such as Germany and France include such powers.

⁴ *Creek v Cairns Post Pty Ltd* (2001) 112 FCR 352, 356-357 [16].

⁵ *Federal Discrimination Law* (Australian Human Rights Commission, 2016) p. 76.
<https://www.humanrights.gov.au/sites/default/files/document/publication/AHRC_Federal%20Discrimination%20Law_2016.pdf>

⁶ (2004) 135 FCR 105, 123

Question 16 to 18

With regards to timing it again depends on the nature of the platform and the content, and again, the clock should start when a user makes the complaint to the platform. Requiring a response only when eSafety makes the request, invites platforms to only act when notified by eSafety, which in turn increase the cost to the public and makes the level of resourcing of eSafety a bottle neck to having a safer Internet for Australians.

If the clock started from notification by a user, with a penalty for failing to remove within 24 hours of user notification, a higher penalty could then apply if there is a continuing breach a certain time period after notification by eSafety. That time period may be a little as an hour for large platforms where there is a reasonable expectation of them having 24 hour support. In this case eSafety itself would also need to operate 24/7 to ensure the scheme could work in practice.

Questions 19-23

The consolidation of takedown powers into a single power is a welcome simplification. This said, some detail may have been lost. The *Classification (Publications, Films and Computer Games) Act 1995* (Cth) s 9A includes a useful provision related to materials which “advocate terrorist acts” which under S 9A(1) “must be classified RC”. While “incitement to violence” would include materials which “advocate terrorist acts”, there is benefit in listing the advocating of terrorist separately. Tackling suck content must be a visible high priority under any new content scheme.

The failure, as reported in the media, to use the existing powers to refer terrorist content to the classifications board is concerning.⁷ Particularly in light of the graph in the consultation document showing just 9 items were actions in 2018-2019 that were outside the category of child sexual abuse material – a dramatic drop compared to previous years. This may indicate more about resourcing and focus than about a lack of other online safety matters that also need attention.

We would recommend that S 9A be part of the new scheme to ensure there is appropriate action on material advocating terrorist acts. We would also recommend there be an obligation to notify the

⁷ Cameron Wilson, “Australia Won't Ban Manifestos Similar To The Christchurch Shooter's Because They Didn't Go As Viral”, BuzzFeed News, 16 January 2020 <<https://www.buzzfeed.com/cameronwilson/australia-manifesto-internet-ban-christchurch-attack>>

classification after a determination in this category so it can also be classified by them as well. This would still be useful for offline formats of, for example, terrorist manifestos.

Overall we believe there is a need to building in a consultative role for civil society and potentially broad and on-going community consultation for the content scheme.

Questions 24-27

The accreditation of tools can be carried out by government on a cost recovery basis from the tool providers. A scheme along this basis rests behind the energy star ratings found on proscribed classes of electrical goods. Fees vary between \$440 and \$780 and are in addition to the costs providing test results or a report from a tester.⁸

While the schemes are voluntary for private use, through agreements with the states they could be made mandatory for schools, libraries and any open internet services provided by parts of government from local municipalities to public venues.

Such accreditation should also require the blocking of additional harmful sites such as phishing sites and (for accreditation for government) sites which fail to comply with Basic Online Safety Expectations (provided, as we suggest, those expectation do not apply unless requested on small services).

Questions 28 to 30

The proposed content blocking scheme is more appropriate than the current arrangements but should be extended to include the hosting of manifesto documents related to the abhorrent violent act and other promotional material prepared in support of the abhorrent violent act. In the case of the Christchurch attack this would include add the manifesto and the Twitter material (photographs of the weapons used), and potentially the post announcing the attack. Appropriate exceptions (rather than defences) should be given for research and journalism.

To advance the aims of the act, it may also be useful have a capacity to maintain a register of organisations (academic research teams, charities, think tanks, consultancy firms) granted an

⁸ Australian Government, Department of the Environment and Energy, "Registration Fees under GEMS Legislation – November 2019"
<<https://www.energyrating.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/Fact%20Sheet%20Registration%20Fees%20November%202019%20FINAL.pdf>>

exception due to work carried out as part of a contract, partnership or collaboration with eSafety, Federal or state police, or parts of the Australian Intelligence Community. Such organisations may need to host the prohibited content in private online services, and in some cases (ideally subject to explicit eSafety approval) may need to host less harmful but still prohibited content in order to test the system.

The process of responding to protect Australians during a crisis (Figure 7 of the consultation document) should be expanded to include relevant civil society groups as part of the response. Civil society groups are already actively engaged,⁹ and in some cases work directly with the major platforms, but this is occurring without collaboration or coordination. By including civil society Australia's capacity can be increased when it is needed most.

The term "online crisis event" may be too broad for what is intended. Thought should be given to whether the definition should be broader, allowing the same power to be used to counter fake news in a cyber-warfare context or foreign interference in elections, or whether the name should be more specific, such as "online promotion of an unfolding or recent abhorrent violent event".

Given the time limited nature, there is a need to continue to have takedown powers (on a more measured basis) for the continued circulation of material from earlier abhorrent violent events. This should feature under the consolidated takedown powers discussed previously.

Questions 31 to 35

There is great value in the ancillary service provider scheme. There is documented evidence that in areas outside of cyberbullying and image-based-abuse, compliance may currently not be so effective. Search engines continue to provide Australians access to terrorist manifestos and at least one refusal to act when it was brought to their attention by civil society has been documented.¹⁰

There should be no need to include searches that are focused internally to a site if the site is itself subject to a requirement to act to remove the content. This said, a platform like Facebook has a

⁹ Andre Oboler, William Allington and Patrick Scolyer-Gray, *Hate and Violent Extremism from an Online Subculture: The Yom Kippur Terrorist Attack in Halle, Germany* (Online Hate Prevention Institute, 2019) p. 100. <<https://ohpi.org.au/hate-and-violent-extremism-from-an-online-subculture-the-yom-kippur-terrorist-attack-in-halle-germany/>>

¹⁰ Ibid p. 51.

search function that allows searching of external links which have been posted to it,¹¹ this feature should be included.

Similar to other parts of the scheme, ancillary service providers should first be notified of problems, and on failing to respond in reasonable time, should be liable to receive a notice. Compliance with the notice should be mandatory.

In order to ease implementation we recommend the legislation clearly state that providing a means, such as a link, to access illegal content is unlawful. A penalty may only apply after a notice is issued, but search engines and platform providers often ask for a reference to which law has been broken. Enabling eSafety, civil society, lawyers and advocates to easier refer to a provision would greatly facilitate voluntary compliance.

Questions 36 to 39

The eSafety Commissioner's functions are fit for purpose but in practice are narrowly construed and predominantly focused on the online safety of children. This is reflected to an extent in the consultation document (e.g. graph at figure 5), information on partnerships, collaborations, grants, etc. Online safety for all Australians could be delivered if the same dedication was applied to other areas of the remit, particular around the provision of funding, and support for partnerships and collaborations. As noted there are numerous points where the proposal sees government and industry coming together without civil society engagement. We would urge a greater focus on facilitating others, particularly civil society, and not just for education but for prevention and response as well.

¹¹ Example of a search for links to eSafety:
https://www.facebook.com/search/links/?q=esafety&epa=SERP_TAB